

ETHNOPHARMACOLOGICAL STUDY OF ANTI-HYPERURICEMIC IN THE DAWUAN REGION, SUBANG, WEST JAVA, INDONESIA

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ABSTRACT

Hyperuricemia and gout became typical metabolic disorders characterized by multiple pathogenic factors. Their incidence increased annually, affecting younger populations. Given that uric acid (UA) and inflammation were the primary disease mechanisms, the search for effective and low-side-effect UA-lowering and anti-inflammatory drugs became a pressing scientific priority. This research aims to document and preserve the use of ethnomedicinal to treat hyperuricemia by communities in the Dawuan Region, Subang, West Java, Indonesia. Fieldwork was carried out from November to December 2025 using direct interviews, questionnaires, and discussions. Plant species are identified based on standard taxonomic methods, flower morphological characteristics, and where possible, using samples for comparison, as well as consultation with experts and the literature. The plant types obtained were grouped into families according to the Cronquist classification system. Plant names were checked against the Plant List (www.plantlist.org) and the International Plant Name Index (www.ipni.org). This research reports that 30 plant species are commonly used by people in the Dawuan Region to treat hyperuricemia. Among the various plant parts used, leaves (56.7%) are most frequently used in making medicines, followed by rhizomes (20.0%), seed (10.0%), fruit (6.7%), stem, and rind (respectively 3.3%). Meanwhile, the most frequently used preparation methods were decoction (80.0%) and infusion (20.0%). The results of this research confirm that people in the Dawuan Region still rely heavily on medicinal plants for their health care system, especially for the treatment of hyperuricemia with the most frequently used parts of the leaves and their use in decoctions and infusions.

KEYWORDS: Traditional medicine, Ethnomedicinal plants, Dawuan Region, Hyperuricemia.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, advancements in living standards and shifts in dietary habits have led to alterations in the body's ability to metabolize. Gout and hyperuricemia (HUA) are typical metabolic disorders arising from this scenario. As the fourth most prevalent disease after hyperglycemia, hyperlipidemia, and hypertension, the incidence of HUA and gout has been steadily increasing in recent years (global prevalence rate: 0.1%–10%).^[1] Meanwhile, gout and HUA are key risk factors for diabetes, hyperglycemia, hyperlipidemia, and hypertension.^[2] Unlike mammals, humans have

relatively high serum uric acid (UA) concentrations (420 $\mu\text{mol/L}$). The absence of uricase in the body hinders the breakdown of UA. HUA serves as the crucial biochemical foundation and direct cause of gout, while gout represents a severe clinical manifestation of HUA. Currently, the global prevalence of gout varies between 0.1% and 10%, generally being higher in developed countries compared to developing ones, especially in North America, Europe, and the United States.^[3] Recently, there has been a new understanding of the disease as a state between HUA and gout called "asymptomatic HUA". The treatment of UA lowering in

patients with asymptomatic HUA remains controversial considering the side effects of chemotherapy and the patient's perceived disease status.^[4,5] New perspectives indicate that inflammation accompanies the entire progression from HUA to gout. Chronic inflammation is already present during the development of HUA. As urate deposits accumulate, the inflammatory cascade escalates into acute inflammation.^[6] To date, gout and HUA pose significant global health threats and are major pressing medical issues worldwide.^[5]

Besides the allopathic medicine, herbal therapy and phytopharmaceuticals are another effective alternative medication. Therefore, the search for alternative treatment of gout has prompted researchers to investigate the beneficial value of natural products. Medicinal plants have been widely used in traditional practices by different ethnic populations throughout the world for the prevention and/or treatment of several chronic diseases. Despite the development of newer technologies and advances in modern medicine, most of the world's population still relies on traditional systems of medicine to fulfill their medical care, especially in Indonesia.^[7] One of the Region in Indonesia that still uses herbal plants as an alternative treatment, especially to treat hyperuricemia, is the Dawuan Region. This research aims to obtain detailed information about the use of herbal plants for alternative therapy for hyperuricemia in Dawuan Region, Subang, West Java, Indonesia using a field survey method.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

Dawuan is located in Subang Regency, West Java, Indonesia, with an area of 88.19 km². This area has an altitude of 700 meters above sea level with an average maximum air temperature of 31°C and a minimum of 24°C. Moreover, it is located between 06°33'31.69" South Latitude and 107°40'55.92" East Longitude. This area is a tropical climate area that is mostly inhabited by Sundanese tribes (90%) and other tribes (10%). Vegetation in the study area is in humid conditions with an average rainfall of 2,500 mm/year.

Data Collection

An extensive field survey was carried out to obtain information about medicinal plants from the Sundanese

tribe in the study area. To document existing information about medicinal plants from tribal practitioners, several field visits were conducted from November to December 2025 in the Dawuan Region, Subang, West Java, Indonesia. During the research, ethnomedicinal information was collected from middle-aged and older tribal practitioners in their local language (Sundanese), through direct interviews, questionnaires, and discussions. Information on local names of plants, plant parts used, preparation methods and administration routes (e.g., infusion, paste, juice and decoction) of all ethnomedicinal plants collected were recorded during the survey period.

Botanical Identification

Plant species are identified based on standard taxonomic methods, flower morphological characteristics, and where possible, using samples for comparison, as well as consultation with experts and the literature.^[8] The plant types obtained were grouped into families according to the Cronquist classification system, except for Pteridophyta and Gymnospermae.^[9] Plant names were checked against the Plant List (www.plantlist.org) and the International Plant Name Index (www.ipni.org).

Ethics Statement

All participants provided verbal consent before the interview and gave consent to publish the information they provided.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research revealed that 30 plant species are commonly used by local people to treat hyperuricemia (Table 1). This shows that the study location is affordable in terms of biodiversity. Among the various plant parts used, leaves (56.7%) are most frequently used in making medicines, followed by rhizomes (20.0%), seed (10.0%), fruit (6.7%), stem, and rind (respectively 3.3%). The use of leaves is reported to be easier to prepare and easier to extract active substances from them for treatment. At the same time, leaves have less effect on the mother plant.^[10] Meanwhile, the most frequently used preparation methods were decoction (80.0%) and infusion (20.0%). These results are in line with previous research which reported that the forms of traditional medicine most widely used by the community were decoctions and infusions.^[8]

Table 1: Ethnomedicinal plants, local name, part used, mode of administration, and dosage uses in Dawuan, Subang, West Java, Indonesia.

No	Species	Family	Local name	Parts used	Mode of administration	Dosage of use
1	<i>Abrus precatorius</i> L.	Fabaceae	Saga	Leaf	Decoction	100 grams once a day
2	<i>Allium sativum</i> L.	Alliaceae	Bawang Putih	Rhizome	Infusion	10 grams once a day
3	<i>Alpinia purpurata</i> K. Schum.	Zingiberaceae	Lengkuas	Rhizome	Decoction	20 grams once a day
4	<i>Andrographis paniculata</i> Nees.	Acanthaceae	Sambiloto	Leaf	Decoction	100 grams once a day
5	<i>Annona muricata</i> L.	Annonaceae	Sirsak	Leaf	Infusion	20 grams once a day

6	<i>Anredera cordifolia</i> (Ten.) Steenis.	Basellaceae	Binahong	Leaf	Decoction	200 grams once a day
7	<i>Apium graveolens</i> L.	Apiaceae	Seledri	Leaf	Decoction	20 grams once a day
8	<i>Carica papaya</i> L.	<u>Caricaceae</u>	Pepaya	Leaf	Decoction	100 grams once a day
9	<i>Cinnamomum verum</i> J.Presl.	Lauraceae	Kayu Manis	Stem	Decoction	80 grams once a day
10	<i>Curcuma longa</i> L.	<u>Zingiberaceae</u>	Kunyit	Rhizome	Infusion	100 grams once a day
11	<i>Curcuma zanthorrhiza</i> Roxb.	Zingiberaceae	Temulawak	Rhizome	Decoction	10 grams once a day
12	<i>Eleutherine palmifolia</i> (L.) Merr.	Iridaceae	Bawang Dayak	Leaf	Decoction	10 grams once a day
13	<i>Garcinia mangostana</i> L.	Clusiaceae	Manggis	Rind	Infusion	50 grams once a day
14	<i>Jatropha gossypifolia</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	Jarak	Leaf	Decoction	20 grams once a day
15	<i>Kaempferia galanga</i> L.	Zingiberaceae	Kencur	Rhizome	Infusion	100 grams once a day
16	<i>Momordica charantia</i> L.	Cucurbitaceae	Pare	Leaf	Decoction	10 grams once a day
17	<i>Morinda citrifolia</i> L.	Rubiaceae	Mengkudu	Fruit	Infusion	50 grams once a day
18	<i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lamk.	<u>Moringaceae</u>	Kelor	Leaf	Decoction	100 grams once a day
19	<i>Myristica fragrans</i> Houtt.	Myristicaceae	Pala	Seed	Decoction	25 grams once a day
20	<i>Nigella sativa</i> L.	Ranunculaceae	Jinten Hitam	Seed	Decoction	100 grams once a day
21	<i>Ocimum tenuiflorum</i> L.	Lamiaceae	Kemangi	Leaf	Decoction	10 grams once a day
22	<i>Orthosiphon aristatus</i> (Blume) Miq.	Lamiaceae	Kumis Kucing	Leaf	Decoction	10 grams once a day
23	<i>Peperomia pellucida</i> Kunth.	Piperaceae	Sirih Cina	Leaf	Decoction	20 grams once a day
24	<i>Persea americana</i> Mill.	Lauraceae	Alpukat	Seed	Decoction	10 grams once a day
25	<i>Phaleria macrocarpa</i> (Scheff.) Boerl.	Thymelaceae	Mahkota Dewa	Fruit	Decoction	20 grams once a day
26	<i>Piper betle</i> L.	Piperaceae	Sirih	Leaf	Decoction	100 grams once a day
27	<i>Sida rhombifolia</i> L.	Malvaceae	Sidaguri	Leaf	Decoction	10 grams once a day
28	<i>Tinospora crispa</i> L.	Menispermaceae	Baratawali	Leaf	Decoction	10 grams once a day
29	<i>Vitex trifolia</i> L.	Lamiaceae	Legundi	Leaf	Decoction	20 grams once a day
30	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> Rosc.	Zingiberaceae	Jahe	Rhizome	Decoction	10 grams once a day

CONCLUSIONS

The results of this research confirm that people in the Dawuan Region still rely heavily on medicinal plants for their health care system, especially for the treatment of hyperuricemia with the most frequently used parts of the leaves and their use in decoctions and infusions.

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